

Predicting Crime in London: Comparing Streetscape Environmental Features Extracted from Images and Social Features

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Summary

Crime rates are influenced by social and streetscape environmental features. Although advancements in machine learning have made it easier to measure these features, many studies have overlooked their predictive potential. To address this gap, this study first randomly sampled 1,000 LSOAs in London, and extracted data on these features to explain variations in crime rates. Then, various models were used to predict crime rates at an additional 500 LSOAs. The findings suggest that allowing for geographical variations is important. Social features to be the most important predictors of crime, but for some crimes, including streetscape environmental features can enhance model's accuracy.

KEYWORDS:

Streetscape environmental features, Social features, Crime prediction, Street view images

1. Introduction

The social and physical dimensions of the environment collectively influence crime distribution. Social features shape social processes that either promote or deter crime (Bottoms, 2012), while physical environmental features serve as measures for crime prevention (Newman, 1977). Considerable previous research has investigated the relationship between the locations of crime and social characteristics of where those crimes took place. This is largely because socioeconomic attributes are easily measured using data like census records (He et al., 2022). As for physical environment, due to limited large-scale detailed data, quantifying it has been more challenging. The recent accessibility of streetscape image data from sources like Google Street View (GSV) has opened new possibilities. As the digital representation most closely resembling the human perspective (Andersson *et al.*, 2017), streetscape images reflect how the environment appears to potential offenders, making them valuable for studying crime patterns. These images can capture micro-scale features of the built environment - such as the structures or appendants of buildings or streets and the signs of physical disorder - that numerous studies have found to be associated with crime (Yue, Liu and Xiao, 2023).

Previous studies have explored the relationship between crime and streetscape environmental features within specific crime types and small areas. However, few have integrated streetscape environmental features with social data for comprehensive analysis, and insights into how these relationships vary across different crimes remain limited. Additionally, there is limited research on utilizing such analyses for crime prediction, leaving a critical gap. By examining London as a case study, the study aims to explore and compare the separate and combined impacts of social features and streetscape environmental features, on the rates of different kinds of crime. Furthermore, it evaluates the effectiveness of statistical models, including traditional regression and machine learning models, in

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predicting crime.

2. Data and methodology

This study focuses on London, using Lower Super Output Areas (LSOAs) as the unit of analysis. A stratified random sampling technique was employed, categorizing LSOAs into deprivation deciles based on a recalibrated Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD) that excluded the crime domain. This approach resulted in a total of 1,500 LSOAs, representing approximately 30% of all LSOAs in London. 1,000 of them were used for training and analysis, and 500 for model testing, while maintaining the same stratified structure based on IMD deciles.

This study used three types of data for analysis: crime rate, streetscape environmental data, and social data. Crime data focuses on six types of street crime: bicycle theft, burglary, criminal damage and arson, robbery, shoplifting, and theft from person. Crime rates are defined as the average annual number of crimes per 1,000 people, calculated using data 2019-2023 obtained from police.uk and averaged over five years. Streetscape environmental data were derived from 451,192 GSV images across 32,747 road segments. Semantic segmentation was performed using the Deeplabv3+ model (Chen *et al.*, 2018), pre-trained on the Cityscapes dataset, to identify 18 environmental features. The average percentages of these features across all images within each LSOA generated its streetscape profile. Social data were sourced from the 2021 Census, OpenStreetMap, and Transport for London, and included characteristics such as ethnic diversity index, vacancy rate, median income, land use (number of POIs), and traffic conditions (transport accessibility scores).

This study utilized Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression models and GWR models to examine the relationship between features and crime rates in 1,000 LSOAs. Four models (OLS, GWR, and two Random Forest models) were used to predict crime rates for 500 additional LSOAs, with one Random Forest model including spatial coordinates to assess geographical influence. Each regression model includes three feature combinations: social features only, streetscape environmental features only, and a combination of both. Relevant social and streetscape environmental features were identified separately for each crime type using stepwise regression. Features from these two groups were then combined to form the third feature set. Before analysis, multicollinearity was ruled out through VIF analysis, and all variables were normalized, log-transformed, and standardized to ensure comparability of coefficients. **Figure 1 and 2** show the overview of the data sources and model description in this study, respectively.

Figure 1 the overview of the data sources

	Analysis	Prediction
OLS regression model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Streetscape environmental features Social features Combination of both 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Streetscape environmental features Social features Combination of both
GWR model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Streetscape environmental features Social features Combination of both 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Streetscape environmental features Social features Combination of both
Random forest model 1		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Streetscape environmental features Social features Combination of both
Random forest model 2		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Streetscape environmental features + longitude and latitude of each LSOA's centroid Social features + longitude and latitude of each LSOA's centroid Combination of both + social features + longitude and latitude of each LSOA's centroid

Figure 2 model description

For the analysis models, OLS regression models assess how well these feature combinations explain the variability in crime rates using statistical metrics. GWR extends this analysis by allowing the relationships between crime rates and predictor variables to vary across space, and evaluates these spatially varying relationships using statistical metrics and Monte Carlo significance tests. During the prediction process, the predictions were compared with actual crime rate to evaluate model performance. Root mean squared error (RMSE) was selected as the accuracy measure to evaluate the prediction effect of the model.

3. Result

The results of OLS regression model show that combining social and streetscape environmental features improves explanatory power for all crimes. For instance, social features explain 52.9% of the variance for robbery, compared to 41.4% for streetscape environmental features. When combined, the model's adjusted R-squared increases to 56.0%. Social features significantly explain the variation in many crime types, but streetscape environmental features are more influential for certain crimes, such as bicycle theft, where they explain 56% of the variance, slightly outperforming social features at 53.2%. **Figure 3** shows the adjusted R-squared summary for the OLS regression model.

	Bicycle theft	Burglary	Criminal damage and arson	Robbery	Shoplifting	Theft from person
Social variables Adjusted R-squared	0.532	0.460	0.407	0.529	0.335	0.656
Streetscape environmental features Adjusted R-squared	0.560	0.341	0.241	0.414	0.271	0.600
Combination of both Adjusted R-squared	0.617	0.472	0.437	0.560	0.373	0.696

Figure 3 the adjusted R-squared of the OLS regression model

The GWR models outperform the OLS models, achieving adjusted R-squared values that are approximately 0.1 higher across crime types. Social features consistently exhibit stronger explanatory power than streetscape environmental features, with models for four of six crimes achieving slightly higher adjusted R-squared values using only social features, as the inclusion of streetscape environmental features can sometimes introduce noise or multicollinearity. For example, theft from person achieves an adjusted R-squared of 0.753 with only social features, compared to 0.748 in combined model. However, combined models perform better for burglary and shoplifting, with adjusted R-squared values increasing by 0.009 and 0.025, respectively. Key variables such as vacancy rate, traffic conditions, road and building exhibit significant spatial variability, highlighting the importance of geographic context in crime analysis. **Figure 4** presents the adjusted R-squared summary for the GWR model.

	Bicycle theft	Burglary	Criminal damage and arson	Robbery	Shoplifting	Theft from person
Social variables Adjusted R-squared	0.733	0.537	0.501	0.613	0.397	0.753
Streetscape environmental features Adjusted R-squared	0.629	0.420	0.322	0.499	0.293	0.665
Combination of both Adjusted R-squared	0.697	0.546	0.500	0.611	0.422	0.748

Figure 4 the adjusted R-squared of the GWR model

For the predictive models, both the GWR and random forest models that include the longitude and latitude of the LSOA centroid demonstrate relatively high predictive accuracy, highlighting the importance of geographic context in understanding crime patterns. Regarding feature combinations, social features generally exhibit stronger predictive power than streetscape environmental features. However, models that incorporate all features tend to achieve the best overall performance across most crime types.

The predictive performance varied across different crime types, with burglary, criminal damage and arson, and robbery demonstrating the highest accuracy. For burglary, the GWR model achieved the lowest RMSE when considering social features alone, while streetscape environmental features also exhibited strong predictive capability, achieving an RMSE of 0.181. Similarly, for criminal damage and arson, the lowest RMSE was obtained using social features, though streetscape environmental features also contributed, with RMSE values remaining around 0.2 across all models. As for robbery, both the GWR model and the random forest model with spatial data showed similar good predictive performance when social features were considered, achieving RMSE values of approximately 0.3. In contrast, bicycle theft, theft from person, and shoplifting showed poorer predictive performance. The highest RMSE values for the first two crimes were around 0.4. Shoplifting exhibited the highest RMSE values (around 0.7), indicating significant prediction errors and outliers. **Figure 5** shows RMSE for predicting six types of crime rate across four models.

Figure 5 RMSE for predicting six types of crime rate across four models

4. Summary

In summary, this study demonstrates the effectiveness of integrating streetscape environmental features from GSV images with social data to explain and predict specific street crimes in London. It achieves key objectives: first, identifying streetscape environmental features most associated with various street crimes, highlighting the complementary roles of streetscape environmental and social features in shaping crime rates. Second, it evaluates multiple models and variable combinations to identify the most effective approaches for predicting crimes, offering valuable insights for crime prevention and urban planning.

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Appendix

Detailed tables and figures related to this study can be accessed at the following link: https://gnotisoug.github.io/PhD/GISRUK2025/GISRUK2025_appendix.htm

Biographies

Sitong Guo

Sitong is a third year PhD student at the School of Geographical Sciences, University of Bristol. Her research focuses on integrating social and environmental features to investigate their influence on crime patterns and distribution through using machine learning techniques and spatial statistical methods.

Richard Harris

Richard is a social geographer interested in socio-spatial inequalities within society and their causes. Presently he is the director of SWDTP and was founding director of the University of Bristol's £1.3 million funded Q-Step Centre. His more recent work has been in urban analytics and cartographic geovisualisation of administrative datasets and in the geographies of education.

Rui Zhu

Rui is a Lecturer in Spatial/Geographical Data Science. Broadly speaking, Rui studies how humans and machines organize spatial knowledge, as well as their interactions with the environment. More specifically, he combines theory-informed (e.g. geography and semantics) and data-driven (e.g. machine learning and spatial statistics) approaches to address geospatial challenges.